

1 **Catalytic site targeting in HER2+ breast cancer for the treatment of CNS metastasis: PSMD4.**

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6 Up to 50% of patients with HER2+ subtype breast cancer develop metastasis to the central nervous
7 system, most commonly the brain, demanding rapid therapeutic approaches to limit spread of the HER2+
8 primary tumor to distant sites (1-3). We recently described the existence of a group of genes that reside
9 proximal to *ERBB2* (the gene that encodes the human epidermal growth factor *HER2*) at 17q12: their
10 differential expression in HER2+ breast cancer, their up-regulation in HER2+ breast cancer, their
11 differential expression and up-regulation in central nervous system (CNS) metastasis and, based on
12 human survival studies, their function in supporting metastasis to the CNS, indicating that the predilection
13 of HER2+ patients to develop CNS metastasis was a phenomena attributable to the disease and not
14 HER2+-targeted therapies (4). Disease recurrence following disease remission (relapse), resistance to
15 trastuzumab or otherwise inadequate long-term control of disease are challenges that limit effectiveness of
16 existing HER2+-targeted therapies. We utilized whole transcriptome technologies (5, 6) to measure total
17 transcription in the brain metastasis of humans with HER2+ breast cancer. We describe here one member
18 of a group of molecules with available catalytic sites for small molecule inhibition that is up-regulated and
19 differentially expressed in CNS metastatic HER2+ breast cancer, PSMD4, as a candidate therapeutic
20 target for the medical management of CNS metastasis in HER2+ breast cancer.
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CRISPR-based reverse genetic screening of human HER2+ organoids or primary tumor cells freshly isolated from patients with HER2+ breast cancer with limited exposure to artificial culture conditions have not yet been described (7, 8). These genetic technologies, though not yet implemented, when done so will likely facilitate discovery of therapeutic vulnerabilities in HER2+ disease with rapidity and ease. Management of major public health problems requires research (bench)-based management in the short run and long run (9). One example of such a major problem is CNS metastasis in HER2+ breast cancer (10-13): this is a type of cancer that affects a human sex with relatively high frequency, a subtype of that cancer that is diagnosed in approximately one quarter of patients diagnosed with that cancer, and a specific complication of the subtype that develops in half of affected patients.

We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the transcriptome (RNA), and epigenetic modification (eg., CpG-DNA) of humans with breast cancer. This includes the primary tumor, the source of the transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - subtypes of the primary tumor, including luminal, basal and HER2+ forms, "regional" metastasis to the lymph nodes, metastasis to distant sites, including the lungs, the liver and the brain, and the circulating tumor stem cell. Our hypothesis and working strategy dictates that in the short-run, disease complications and therapeutic limitations are best managed using identification of therapeutic targets by whole transcriptome differential expression analyses (subtraction analysis), and in the long-run, will be enhanced and fully complemented by reverse genetic screening strategies to blindly identify disease-specific, subtype-specific and metastasis-specific therapeutic vulnerabilities augmented by novel immunotherapy approaches. Here we describe one such target identified through rigorous study of the HER2+ CNS metastasis transcriptome: a therapeutic target with an available catalytic site that is up-regulated and metastasis-specific: PSMD4.

Results

Figure 1: PSMD4 is differentially expressed in HER2+ breast cancer.

I. Brain metastases and primary tumors from humans with breast cancer: HER2+ subtype

n=8 primary tumors from humans with HER2+ breast cancer

n=5 brain metastases (tumor) from humans with HER2+ breast cancer (breast; human; HER2+)

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
5710	4.81E-03	0.2666	-2.8196149	-0.75161064	4200.15	PSMD4	3819/21403	78.5

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the normal breast tissue and in primary tumors of humans with HER2+ breast cancer (5), we discovered differential expression of proteasome 26S subunit ubiquitin receptor, non-ATPase 4, encoded by *PSMD4* in CNS metastatic HER2+ breast cancer in humans (**Chart 1**). The expression of PSMD4 changed more than 78% of the human CNS metastatic transcriptome in HER2+ breast cancer when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 21,403 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of PSMD4 messenger RNA in HER2+ brain metastases, demonstrating up-regulation of PSMD4 during disease progression in the HER2+ breast cancer subtype.

II. Brain metastases and primary tumors from humans with breast cancer.

n=11 tumors from humans with HER2+ breast cancer

n=3 brain metastases (tumor) from humans with HER2+ breast cancer (breast; human; HER2+)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
20474	1.51E-01	1.52	-5.0427	3.86E-01	PSMD4	5371/17581	69.4

1 In a second microarray dataset (6) from independent investigators and a separate patient cohort, we
2 observed differential expression of PSMD4 in breast cancer CNS metastasis in humans, but expression of
3 PSMD4 here was decreased (**Chart 2**).

4 Nevertheless, we concluded that differential and increased expression of PSMD4 likely defined the
5 CNS metastatic transcriptome in human breast cancer.

6 **Discussion**

7 Adjunctive treatments in medical oncology limit the emergence of resistant tumor clones during
8 treatment with a second agent (whether neoadjuvantive chemotherapy or a targeted therapy like
9 trastuzumab). Small molecule inhibitors of PSMD4, once evaluated for toxicity and safety, can immediately
10 be tested for efficacy in patients with HER2+ metastasis, with the goal of identifying the most effective
11 small molecules for chemotherapeutic management of HER2+ disease in humans. We recently used
12 primary tumor transcriptome data to identify multiple phosphatases that we deemed candidate therapeutic
13 targets in management of breast cancer, and fortuitously found their decreased expression was
14 specifically linked to superior overall survival in patients with HER2+ breast cancer (14, 15). A
15 multi-kinase approach delivered in conjunction with chemotherapies that target dNTP synthesis,
16 replication of the daughter strand and activity at the spindle at anaphase is most likely to be most effective
17 in limiting tumor clone resistance (16).
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Methods

We utilized GSE191230 for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in metastasis to the CNS and in primary tumors from humans with breast cancer (along with GSE10893 for target validation) using RNA-sequencing and microarray data (published) and R-based computational methods.